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The Editor-in-Chief

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**Hopelessness and Emotional Vulnerability as Drivers of Cannabis Use Disorder among
Young Adults in Nigeria**

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Abstract

Nigerian youths are facing increasing risk of cannabis use disorder (CUD), driven by psychosocial stressors and underlying psychological vulnerabilities. This study examined hopelessness and emotional vulnerability as predictors of cannabis use disorder among young adults in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Using an ex-post facto design, data were collected from 210 participants. Standardized instruments (the Beck Hopelessness Scale, Difficulties in Emotion Regulation Scale, and Cannabis Use Disorder Identification Test-Revised) were administered. Results revealed that males reported significantly higher hopelessness than females ($t=2.31, p < .05$), while age significantly influenced both hopelessness ($F = 3.82, p < .05$) and emotional vulnerability ($F = 4.10, p < .05$). Correlation analysis showed that hopelessness ($r = .21, p < .05$) and emotional vulnerability ($r = .27, p < .05$) were positively associated with CUD. Multiple regression confirmed both variables as significant predictors, with emotional vulnerability ($\beta = .42, p < .05$) emerging as a stronger factor than hopelessness ($\beta = .34, p < .05$), jointly explaining 34% of the variance in cannabis use disorder. These findings underscore the critical role of negative future expectations and emotion dysregulation in shaping cannabis-related problems among Nigerian youth. The study recommends targeted interventions to reduce hopelessness, enhance emotional regulation, and integrate psychosocial support into prevention programs to curb rising CUD prevalence.

Keywords: Cannabis Use Disorder, Hopelessness, Emotional Vulnerability, Young Adults

Introduction

Young adults across the globe are increasingly exposed to the risk of cannabis and other psychoactive substance use because of interacting social, psychological, and developmental factors that characterise this stage of life. During young adulthood, individuals often experience heightened emotional instability, identity exploration, and increased exposure to peer influence, all of which make cannabis use a relatively common phenomenon and increase vulnerability to the development of substance use disorders. In Nigeria, this concern is particularly pronounced because, despite cannabis remaining an illicit substance, accumulating evidence indicates a steady rise in its use, especially among young adults (Olashore et al., 2020). This trend is troubling given that cannabis use disorder (CUD) is associated with a wide range of adverse psychosocial and health outcomes, including depression, anxiety, suicidal ideation, impaired academic functioning, and broader social maladjustment (Vidal et al., 2023; Gobbi et al., 2019). While public and scholarly attention to cannabis-related problems has increased, existing Nigerian research has largely concentrated on prevalence and social correlates, with limited empirical focus on the intrinsic psychological factors that predispose young people to harmful cannabis use. Key vulnerabilities such as hopelessness and emotional vulnerability remain underexplored, despite evidence suggesting that they play a central role in shaping maladaptive coping behaviours and the progression to cannabis use disorder among young adults.

The term hopelessness or negative expectancies of the future, is strongly associated with depression, suicidal ideation, and adaptive coping behavior, including substance use (Iweama et al., 2024). On the other hand, emotional vulnerability, including the lack of ability to control emotions, hyper-responsivity to stress, and ineffective coping mechanisms, have also been associated with hazardous health behavior and substance dependence (Wisener et al., 2020; Weidberg et al., 2023). Evidence from Western and African environments alike shows that these psychological variables robustly predict cannabis use and cannabis problems (Moreno-Mansilla et al., 2021; Buckner et al., 2017). Evidence have shown that the use of cannabis among young adults is consistently associated with adverse psychological and social effects. For instance, it has been proven that young people who consume cannabis have higher tendencies to develop depression, anxiety, and suicidal thoughts compared to non-consumers (Vidal et al., 2023). These findings in North America and Europe point to the fact that cannabis use disorder is linked with higher psychiatric comorbidity risk, worsening academic performance, and psychosocial impairment (Sorkhou et al., 2024; Morissette et al., 2023). In

Botswana, Olashore et al. (2020) found that university first-year students were faced with a prevalence rate of cannabis use disorder, while low religiosity and academic pressure were reported as significant risk factors. Both emotional and psychosocial vulnerabilities are suggested to be the cause of the cannabis-related activities by these findings.

Hopelessness is uncovered as being a particularly strong predictor of the initiation and maintenance of substance use. Hopeless youth are more likely to start using cannabis at a young age and continue using it as a coping mechanism for distress (Assari et al., 2025; Moreno-Mansilla et al., 2021). Nigerian studies also discover that hopelessness is a strong predictor of suicidal ideation and substance use behaviour among undergraduate students, confirming its relevance in Africa (Iweama et al., 2024). Globally, hopelessness has been shown to mediate the connection between emotional distress and poor health behaviors, further establishing its status as a psychological driver for drug use (Moore et al., 2025).

Emotional vulnerability, normally quantified in the form of emotion dysregulation, has also been closely linked with cannabis use. Impoverished emotion regulation capacity among young adults increases their susceptibility to the use of cannabis as a maladaptive coping strategy, thus heightened risk for dependence (Weidberg et al., 2023; Wisener et al., 2020). Empirical research further shows that females may be particularly at risk in terms of heightened sensitivity to emotional pain and greater vulnerability to substance use for coping reasons (Thompson et al., 2024). Studies in contexts reveal that cannabis use disorder is not a product of availability but also highly dependent on inherent vulnerabilities. Emotional dysregulation accounts for the connection between cannabis use and adverse mental health outcomes (Weidberg et al., 2023), while hopelessness predicts substance initiation and maintenance during adolescence and early adulthood (Assari et al., 2025; Moreno-Mansilla et al., 2021).

Whilst prevalence and correlates of cannabis use amongst Nigerian students have been explored before (Mokuolu et al., 2015; Olashore et al., 2020), very few or no studies have explored these underlying psychological mechanisms, or points towards hopelessness and emotional vulnerability as significant psychological correlates of cannabis use disorder. The situation calls even for more careful examination in the face of rising youth unemployment, financial strain, and social unrest within the Nigerian environment. This study therefore seeks to examine hopelessness and emotional vulnerability as predictors of cannabis use disorder in Nigerian youth. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

- i. finds out the influence of gender, age, and religion on hopelessness and emotional vulnerability among young adults in Nigeria
- ii. investigate the predictive role of hopelessness on cannabis use disorder among young adults in Nigeria
- iii. examine the effect of emotional vulnerability on cannabis use disorder young adults in Nigeria

Methods

Design and sampling technique

This study employed the ex-post facto research design in exploring the variations in hopelessness, emotional vulnerability, and impact on cannabis use disorder among Nigerian young adults. The study population comprised in Nigeria, operationally defined as individuals aged between 18 and 35 years, in line with the African Union's definition of youth. This population segment was chosen because it represents the demographic group most at risk of cannabis experimentation and progression to substance use disorder (Olashore et al., 2020; Vidal et al., 2023). The sample included both students and non-students to capture broader socio-demographic and psychosocial dynamics beyond the university setting. Geographically, the study is delimited to Ekiti State. For representativeness, the three geo-political zones in Ekiti (South, North and Central) were purposively selected, reflecting areas with higher reports of cannabis cultivation, availability, and use.

The study participants were selected using the multistage sampling technique. At the first stage, the purposive sampling technique was employed to identify the youths with cases of cannabis use disorder and at the second stage snowball referrals were used to reach additional participants, especially those hesitant to disclose cannabis use publicly. This approach was necessary given the illicit nature of cannabis in Nigeria and the hidden nature of the population. A total of 210 participants were obtained in all and considered relevant for the study.

Measures

The study employed a structured questionnaire divided into three major sections. Section A elicited demographic data such as age, gender, and religion, which were included as control and comparative variables in the analysis.

Hopelessness. was measured using the Beck Hopelessness Scale (BHS) developed by Beck, Weissman, Lester, and Trexler (1974). The BHS is a 20-item self-report inventory designed to

assess negative expectancies about the future. Each item is scored in a true/false format, with higher scores reflecting greater hopelessness. The scale has been widely validated, including among African populations, and demonstrates good internal consistency, with Cronbach's alpha coefficients ranging between .82 and .93 in prior studies.

Emotional vulnerability. This construct was measured using the Difficulties in Emotion Regulation Scale (DERS), developed by Gratz and Roemer (2004). DERS is a 36-item scale that captures six dimensions of emotion regulation difficulties: non-acceptance, goals, impulse, awareness, strategies, and clarity. Responses are rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = almost never to 5 = almost always). Higher scores indicate greater emotional vulnerability. The DERS has consistently demonstrated high reliability ($\alpha = .92$ overall) and cross-cultural validity, making it appropriate for the Nigerian context. The last part of the questionnaire which is section D assessed cannabis use disorder using the Cannabis Use Disorder Identification Test-Revised (CUDIT-R), developed by Adamson et al. (2010). The CUDIT-R is an 8-item screening tool designed to identify patterns of harmful cannabis use over the past six months. Items are scored on a Likert scale ranging from 0 to 4, with a total score above 12 suggesting probable cannabis use disorder. The tool has shown robust psychometric properties, with sensitivity and specificity indices exceeding 80% in different populations. Its brevity and clarity made it suitable for use with diverse Nigerian young adult respondents.

Procedure

Data used for the study was collected with the help of three trained field assistants familiar with the study communities. Ethical Approval was obtained from the Centre for Research and Development, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti. Participants were provided with informed consent forms detailing the purpose of the research, the confidentiality of responses, and the voluntary nature of participation. Given the sensitivity of the subject, respondents were assured of anonymity, and questionnaires were completed privately. Data obtained were coded and structured on Google Sheets and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27.

Data analysis

Descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviations, and frequency distributions were used to summarize demographic and study variables. Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to examine bivariate associations among hopelessness, emotional vulnerability, and cannabis use disorder. Independent t-tests and one-way ANOVA were used to examine the role of

demographic factors (gender, age group, and religion) on hopelessness and emotional vulnerability. Finally, multiple regression analysis was employed to determine the joint and unique contributions of hopelessness and emotional vulnerability in predicting cannabis use disorder. All tests were conducted at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

<i>Variable</i>		<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Gender	Male	166	79.1
	Female	44	20.9
	Total	210	100.0
Age (in years)	18 – 25	112	53.3
	26 – 35	98	46.7
	Total	210	100.0
Religion	Christianity	135	64.3
	Islamic	58	27.6
	Traditional	17	8.1
	Total	210	100.0

It is evident in Table 1 that majority of the respondents were male (79.1%), with a few females (20.9%). Most respondents were aged 18–25 years (53.3%), with 46.7% of them aged 26–35 years. In terms of religion, Christianity dominated (64.3%), followed by Islam (27.6%), with a minority identifying with traditional beliefs (8.1%). This truly reflects the demographic characteristics of the youths of the study area.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix of the Variables

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>
Hopelessness	18.42	5.21	1		
Emotional Vulnerability	21.67	6.45	.18*	1	
Cannabis Use Disorder (CUD)	15.93	4.88	.21*	.27**	1

* $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$

Hopelessness showed a positive correlation with emotional vulnerability ($r = .18, p < .05$), indicating that individuals with negative expectations about the future are more likely to struggle with regulating emotions. Both hopelessness ($r = .21, p < .05$) and emotional vulnerability ($r = .27, p < .01$) were positively linked with CUD, suggesting that higher levels of these psychological factors increase the likelihood of problematic cannabis use.

Table 3: Independent t-test of Gender Differences in Hopelessness and Emotional Vulnerability

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Hopelessness	Male	19.05	5.12	2.31	0.022
	Female	17.10	5.28		
Emotional Vulnerability	Male	22.14	6.63	1.96	0.052
	Female	20.52	6.01		

In Table 3, the independent t-test results revealed that there is a significant gender difference in hopelessness between male and female respondents ($t=2.31, p<0.05$), with males ($M = 19.05, SD = 5.12$) reporting higher levels than females ($M = 17.10, SD = 5.28$). This could imply that male young adults experience greater negative expectations about the future compared to females. For emotional vulnerability, males ($M = 22.14, SD = 6.63$) also reported slightly higher scores than females ($M = 20.52, SD = 6.01$). However, this difference is not significant ($t = 1.96, p = .052$).

Table 4: One-Way ANOVA of Age and Religion on Hopelessness and Emotional

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Source</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Hopelessness	Age	142.3	2	71.2	3.82	0.024
	Religion	95.6	2	47.8	2.41	0.092
Emotional Vulnerability	Age	156.4	2	78.2	4.1	0.018
	Religion	112.8	2	56.4	2.95	0.055

The ANOVA results presented in Table 4 revealed that age significantly influenced hopelessness ($F = 3.82, p < .05$) and emotional vulnerability ($F = 4.10, p < .05$), indicating variations across age groups. Religion, however, had no significant effect on hopelessness ($F = 2.41, p > .05$) or emotional vulnerability ($F = 2.95, p > .05$), though the latter showed a marginal trend. This suggests age is a stronger determinant of these psychological factors than religion.

Table 5: Multiple Regression Summary Table on Hopelessness and Emotional Vulnerability as Predictors of Cannabis Use Disorder (CUD)

<i>Predictor Variable</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>β</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p-value</i>
Hopelessness	0.42	0.08	0.34	5.25	0.018
Emotional Vulnerability	0.51	0.07	0.42	7.29	0.003

Model Summary: $R^2 = 0.34$; Adj. $R^2 = 0.33$; $F(2,207) = 120.65$; $p < 0.001$

The regression results revealed that both hopelessness and emotional vulnerability significantly predict cannabis use disorder among young adults. Hopelessness ($B = 0.42, \beta = 0.34, t = 5.25, p < 0.05$) positively predicted cannabis use disorder, indicating that higher levels of hopelessness are associated with greater cannabis-related problems. Similarly, emotional

vulnerability ($B = 0.51$, $\beta = 0.42$, $t = 7.29$, $p < .05$) was a stronger predictor, suggesting that difficulties in regulating emotions are more strongly linked to cannabis use disorder. The overall model was highly significant, $F(2, 207) = 120.65$, $p < .05$, explaining 34% of the variance in cannabis use disorder ($\text{Adj. } R^2 = .33$), which demonstrates a strong predictive power of the psychological variables.

Discussion

Findings on the influence of gender, age and religion on hopelessness and emotional vulnerability to cannabis use disorder among Nigerian young adults revealed these variables determine the psychological orientations that lead young adults to cannabis use disorder, with gender and age being more stable determinants compared to religion. Previous research has similarly demonstrated that young men are more susceptible to demonstrating maladaptive coping reactions, including substance use, due to cultural expectations and less help-seeking behavior compared to women (Atilola 2014; Olashore et al., 2020). Age variations in emotional vulnerability and hopelessness are similarly well-documented, as emerging adulthood is also a period marked by identity seeking, exposure to psychosocial stressors, and uncertainty about the future, each of which can heighten susceptibility to substance use (Moreno-Mansilla et al., 2021). In Nigeria, this developmental vulnerability is compounded by structural challenges such as youth unemployment and limited social mobility which exacerbates psychological distress and substance use risk (Gureje et al., 2015) this is Even though religion has been more commonly involved as a protective factor against substance use (Olashore et al., 2020), its weaker influence in this context suggests that religiosity in Nigeria may not be intense enough to moderate the influence of psychological risk factors.

On the second objective which explores the predictive role of hopelessness in cannabis use disorder among young adults. The results confirm that hopelessness, a cognitive schema characterized by negative expectations of the future, is a key psychological determinant of substance use. This finding agrees with the literature showing that hopeless youth are more likely to initiate and persist in cannabis use as a maladaptive way of escape from pain and uncertainty (Assari et al., 2025; Moreno-Mansilla et al., 2021). In the Nigerian context, where economic instability, unemployment, and limited opportunities worsen existential insecurity, hopelessness was found to be significantly correlated with maladaptive coping, suicidal ideation, and substance use (Atilola et al., 2014; Iweama et al., 2024). Hopelessness has been

theoretically constructed globally as a mediating process between emotional distress and risky health behaviors (Moore et al., 2025), further explaining its role in predicting cannabis abuse.

Examining the role of emotional vulnerability in cannabis use disorder in young adults, findings demonstrate that emotional vulnerability, as typically measured in terms of emotion dysregulation, is a particularly strong predictor of cannabis use disorder. The finding contributes to the large body of evidence showing that deficits in emotional regulation capacity heighten the risk of substance dependence (Weidberg et al., 2023; Wisener et al., 2020). Young adults who are unable to regulate stressful emotions often turn to cannabis use as a maladaptive emotion regulation technique, thereby increasing their risk for cannabis use disorder. The literature highlights that while hopelessness explains risk trajectories over the long term, emotional dysregulation usually operates as the proximal factor exerting direct influence on the escalation into problematic cannabis use (Thompson et al., 2024). Also, the gendered quality of emotional vulnerability from previous studies, in which women are particularly sensitive to emotional pain and men externalize through risk-taking, can also explain how emotional dysregulation operates differently within populations (Wisener et al., 2020).

It is evident that psychological variables such as hopelessness do not occur in isolation but are shaped by systemic stressors which includes poverty, insecurity and limited access to mental health services. The theoretical implication of this study is evident in its support to cognitive-affective vulnerability and stress-coping models of substance use and abuse by confirming that hopelessness and emotional dysregulation are critical determinants of cannabis use disorder among Nigerian young adults (Beck et al., 1974; Wills & Shiffman, 1985). The significance of gender and age effects is also consistent with developmental models of substance use and abuse, which underscore the impact of sociocultural expectations and age-related challenges on substance use vulnerability (Adewuya, 2016). The practical implications of these findings reflects the importance of culturally relevant interventions that would address emotion regulation and cognitive restructuring of hopelessness among young adults.

Conclusion

It is evident in this study that hopelessness and emotional vulnerability are significant psychological predictors of cannabis use disorder among young adults in Nigeria, with demographic factors such as gender and age exerting additional influence. This therefore emphasized that negative future expectations and poor emotional regulation capacity are

central drivers of cannabis use disorder, consistent with evidence from global and African contexts. By focusing on these psychological mechanisms, the study advances understanding of the underlying vulnerabilities that contribute to cannabis-related problems among Nigerian youth. Based on these insights, it is recommended that prevention and intervention programs integrate psychological support aimed at reducing hopelessness and strengthening emotional regulation skills. Schools, universities, and community health centers should implement resilience-building programs, peer support systems, and mental health awareness campaigns to address the underlying risks. Policy interventions should also prioritize youth empowerment through employment opportunities and social support systems to reduce feelings of hopelessness. Future research should further deepen understanding of how these psychological factors evolve and influence cannabis use behaviors over time, while documenting influence of cultural variations.

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